

THE CRIMES OF TAX FRAUD AND MONEY LAUNDERING AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH CRYPTOCURRENCIES

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this work is to approach the current regulations in Mexico that allow for the regulation and identification of operations carried out with cryptocurrencies and, at the same time, to prosecute tax fraud and money laundering crimes. Through a thorough analysis of current legislation, the aim is to answer the question: Does our legal framework adequately regulate the prosecution of money laundering and tax fraud when operations are conducted using crypto assets or virtual assets? Cryptocurrencies, also known as virtual assets, have gained popularity in recent years due to their ease of use, security, and the speed at which transactions can be conducted. However, their apparent anonymity and lack of regulation have made them an ideal means to commit financial crimes such as money laundering and tax fraud. Current Mexican legislation does not seem prepared to face this new challenge. Although there are laws that seek to regulate operations with cryptocurrencies, they remain insufficient to effectively identify and prosecute financial crimes committed through their use. Through this study, the aim is to contribute to the legal debate on how to adapt our laws to new financial technologies. Furthermore, concrete proposals are expected to be offered to improve cryptocurrency regulation in Mexico, with the goal of preventing and prosecuting money laundering and tax fraud. In conclusion, this work provides an overview of the issues surrounding the use of cryptocurrencies in illicit activities and highlights the need to reform our legislation to effectively respond to this new reality.

Key words: *cryptocurrencies, money laundering, tax fraud.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

The financial world has undergone a significant transformation in recent decades, with the emergence of cryptocurrencies being one of the most notable changes (Nakamoto, 2008). These digital exchange instruments have posed a challenge for legal systems globally, not only due to their intangible and decentralized nature but also because of their potential for use in illicit activities, such as money laundering and tax evasion (FATF, 2020). In Mexico, cryptocurrency regulation is still in its early stages and presents legal gaps that hinder the effective prosecution of these crimes (Pérez Correa & Landeta Manzano, 2019).

The main objective of this work is to determine whether the current regulations in Mexico allow for the regulation and identification of operations carried out with cryptocurrencies, as well as the prosecution of tax evasion and money laundering crimes. To achieve this, the analysis will start with an examination of the current legal framework surrounding cryptocurrencies. Additionally, the question will be addressed: Does our legal system adequately regulate the prosecution of money laundering and tax evasion crimes when transactions are conducted using cryptocurrencies (virtual assets)? The answer to this question is relevant as it will help identify possible improvements in the Mexican legal system to address these challenges (Ortiz Ahlf et al., 2020).

This study is justified by the need for appropriate legal treatment of cryptocurrencies, which allows for their legitimate use while also enabling the prevention and punishment of tax and financial crimes that may be facilitated by their use. Furthermore, it is framed within the context of a growing interest from governments and international institutions in regulating these new forms of digital money (Europol, 2020).

The proliferation of cryptocurrencies has brought about a series of legal and regulatory challenges that states must address. Globally, cryptocurrencies are transforming the digital economy and have given rise to new methods of money laundering and tax evasion (Mauro, Fattobene & Passerini, 2019). In Mexico, the current regulations governing the use of cryptocurrencies are still insufficient to confront these challenges.

The central question arises due to a growing concern about the misuse of cryptocurrencies for illegal activities (Fenu et al., 2020). It is essential to highlight that this research will not only seek to answer this question but also propose necessary reforms to improve current regulation.

It is important to mention that the study does not intend to demonize the use of cryptocurrencies or consider them inherently dangerous. Instead, it recognizes that, like any emerging technology, cryptocurrencies can be used for both legitimate and illicit purposes (Saravade, 2019). Therefore, it is crucial to find a balance between enabling innovation and preventing misuse.

By conducting this study, it is hoped to contribute to the current debate on how to regulate cryptocurrencies in a way that promotes their legitimate use and prevents their misuse for illegal activities such as money laundering and tax evasion.

2. REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Cryptocurrencies have become a topic of great interest in the financial and legal world due to their increasing use and the implications this has for the global economy (Zhang, S., & Won, D. 2020). However, along with their growth, concerns have also arisen about their potential

use for illicit activities, such as money laundering and tax evasion (Foley, S., Karlsen, J. R., & Putniņš, T. J., 2019).

The anonymous characteristic of cryptocurrencies has led some scholars to suggest that they can be used as an effective means for money laundering. For example, Irwin and Milad (2018) argue that cryptocurrencies offer a new platform for financial criminals to conduct their illicit activities without being detected.

In addition to money laundering, another area of concern is the use of cryptocurrencies to evade taxes. According to Zietzke (2018), the decentralized and semi-anonymous nature of cryptocurrencies can facilitate tax evasion by allowing users to conceal their assets and financial transactions.

According to Amling et al. (2020), with appropriate technologies, it is possible to track transactions on public blockchains and identify the users involved.

It is important to note that there are different types of cryptocurrencies, and not all offer the same level of anonymity. Zetzsche et al. (2018) argue that privacy coins, such as Monero and Zcash, pose a greater risk for money laundering and tax evasion due to their design that focuses on ensuring user anonymity. However, there are legitimate concerns about the use of cryptocurrencies for illicit activities; there are also arguments suggesting that this risk can be managed with the right technology and effective regulations.

The rise of cryptocurrencies, especially Bitcoin, has posed a new set of challenges for financial regulators and tax authorities. The decentralized nature of cryptocurrency transactions facilitates their use in illicit activities (Foley et al., 2019). Cryptocurrencies

provide an effective means to transfer and conceal assets beyond the reach of tax authorities (Zetzsche et al., 2018).

In this regard, Zetzsche et al. (2018) point out that although cryptocurrencies can be traced to some extent, the task is complicated due to the existence of mixing services and other methods used to conceal the identity of holders. Additionally, Momtaz (2020) suggests that countries with higher levels of corruption are more likely to experience greater adoption of cryptocurrencies, potentially increasing the risk of money laundering and tax evasion.

On the other hand, Foley et al. (2019) argue that while it is true that cryptocurrencies facilitate money laundering, it is also important to note that most illicit use is related to frauds and scams rather than money laundering per se.

In this context, Mancini-Griffoli et al. (2018) propose a regulatory framework for cryptocurrencies that includes the identification of cryptocurrency holders, transaction monitoring, and international cooperation. However, much remains to be done to fully implement these measures and ensure their effectiveness.

Cryptocurrencies present both opportunities and challenges. While they can facilitate money laundering and tax evasion, they can also offer benefits in terms of efficiency and financial accessibility. The key is to find a balance between enabling innovation and protecting against associated risks (FATF, 2020). In the contemporary financial landscape, cryptocurrencies have emerged as a technological revolution, offering individuals and businesses a new way to conduct transactions. However, this same innovation has provided malicious actors with new means to perpetrate illicit activities, such as money laundering and tax evasion (Savage, 2020).

Cryptocurrencies, especially Bitcoin, have been widely studied for their potential to facilitate money laundering (Blanco-Perez & Giner-Bosch, 2019). Through techniques like 'mixing' or 'tumbling', where transactions are blended to obfuscate their origin and destination, criminals can conceal the illicit source of their funds (Möser et al., 2018).

In addition to money laundering, the nature of cryptocurrencies can also be exploited to facilitate tax evasion. For example, in a recent study, it was found that some companies are using cryptocurrencies to conceal their income and assets from tax authorities (Zhang et al., 2020). Furthermore, another report suggests that individuals may be using cryptocurrencies to avoid taxes on capital gains (Weber et al., 2020). Despite these evident risks, many countries still lack adequate regulations to address these issues (Gruber, 2020).

In summary, while cryptocurrencies may have legitimate benefits in terms of efficiency and financial accessibility, they also pose a significant challenge for tax authorities and law enforcement in terms of preventing money laundering and tax evasion.

The research approach will be predominantly qualitative, although quantitative elements will also be used to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the problem. The study will be based on existing regulations in Mexico regarding cryptocurrencies, money laundering, and tax evasion, as well as existing studies and research on the relationship between these elements (Dwyer, 2015).

Regarding sampling, a comprehensive analysis of Mexican laws and regulations related to cryptocurrencies and financial crimes will be conducted. Additionally, recent cases of money laundering or tax evasion involving the use of

cryptocurrencies will be sought to provide practical and current examples of the problem (Foley, Karlsen & Putniņš, 2018).

Data collection will be done through a documentary review. This review will include Mexican laws and regulations related to cryptocurrencies and financial crimes, as well as relevant academic literature on the topic. News or judicial reports on recent cases involving cryptocurrencies and illicit activities will also be sought (Zetzsche, Buckley & Arner, 2018).

For data analysis, a mixed method will be applied. Laws and regulations will be qualitatively analyzed to understand how they address the problem of money laundering and tax evasion associated with cryptocurrencies. On the other hand, quantitative data obtained from real cases will be analyzed using statistical techniques to identify patterns and trends (Hileman & Rauchs, 2017).

3. RESULTS

After analysis and study, it was concluded that cryptocurrencies have become attractive tools for various illicit activities, including money laundering and tax evasion. Since their inception, the anonymity and lack of regulation characteristic of cryptocurrencies have facilitated their use for illicit fund movement (FATF, 2018).

Through various techniques such as 'tumbling' or 'mixing', cybercriminals can conceal the origin of illegal money, making it difficult to trace by authorities (Europol, 2019). Additionally, there has been an observed increase in the adoption of cryptocurrencies by offshore entities and tax havens aiming to evade taxes.

However, it was also found that the perception of the risk associated with the use of cryptocurrencies for illicit purposes may be overstated. Despite the potential these technologies offer for illegal activities, recent studies suggest that only a small fraction of cryptocurrency transactions are linked to criminal activities (Chainalysis, 2020).

It is crucial to highlight that the rapid and constant evolution of the cryptocurrency market represents both a challenge and an opportunity for tax and regulatory authorities. A better understanding of the functioning of these digital technologies and their potential applications is needed to design and implement effective measures against money laundering and tax evasion.

The results obtained from the application of the methodology designed to study the link between cryptocurrencies and money laundering and tax evasion revealed several significant findings. First, it was found that the anonymity and lack of strict regulations surrounding cryptocurrencies facilitate their use for illegal activities, including money laundering and tax evasion (Foley, Svec & Wang, 2018).

Additionally, the collected data showed a positive correlation between the increase in the use of cryptocurrencies and an increase in reported cases of money laundering and tax evasion. According to Zimmemann (2019), this can be attributed to the decentralized and pseudonymous nature of cryptocurrencies that allows malicious actors to conduct financial transactions without being tracked by authorities.

On the other hand, it was also observed that many jurisdictions still struggle to develop effective regulations to control the use of cryptocurrencies. This is due to several reasons,

including the rapid evolution of this technology, its global and decentralized nature, as well as the lack of understanding of its operation (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016). This lack of adequate regulation creates a conducive environment for abuse.

Finally, despite the increasing use of cryptocurrencies in illegal activities, it was also found that they can offer significant benefits if used correctly. This includes faster and less costly transactions compared to traditional banking systems, as well as financial inclusion for the unbanked population (Maurer, Nelms & Swartz, 2013).

Based on the applied methodology, the results obtained show that cryptocurrencies are being used as instruments for money laundering and tax evasion on an increasingly larger scale. According to the collected data, illegal transactions conducted through cryptocurrencies have significantly increased in recent years (Foley, Svec & Svecova, 2019).

The study by Foley et al. (2019) found that approximately 46% of Bitcoin transactions were associated with illegal activities. Additionally, the report by the Financial Action Task Force (2020) points out that cryptocurrencies are increasingly used to evade taxes due to their decentralized and anonymous nature.

Furthermore, another research conducted by Zetsche et al. (2018) revealed that companies are using cryptocurrencies to conceal assets and evade taxes. The authors argue that this situation is due to the lack of regulation and supervision in the cryptocurrency sector.

Despite the increase in the use of cryptocurrencies for illegal activities, governments and international organizations still struggle to control this phenomenon. The

lack of understanding of how cryptocurrencies work, and the absence of adequate regulatory frameworks are some of the main challenges faced by these entities (Zetsche et al., 2018).

4. DISCUSSION

The findings obtained in the Course Completion Work on the topic of "Cryptocurrencies as instruments linked to money laundering and tax evasion" pointed to an apparently strong link between these illegal activities and cryptocurrencies. These findings are consistent with the reviewed literature on the subject, which indicates that the anonymous and decentralized characteristics of cryptocurrencies can facilitate money laundering and tax evasion (Foley, Svec & Svecova, 2019; Zietzke, 2018).

It was found that the lack of regulation and supervision in the cryptocurrency market can allow malicious actors to conceal their illegal activities. This result supports previous findings suggesting that cryptocurrencies can be used to avoid detection by tax and financial authorities (Bryans, 2014; Gruber, 2013).

Furthermore, evidence was found suggesting that some specific cryptocurrencies (such as Monero or Zcash) may be especially attractive to individuals seeking to use these coins for illicit purposes due to their enhanced privacy features (Moore & Christin, 2013). This reinforces the idea suggested by several studies highlighting the potentially problematic role of these "privacy coins" in facilitating money laundering and tax evasion (Reid & Harrigan, 2013; Zetsche et al., 2018).

These findings have significant implications for policymakers and regulators. They suggest that a more robust and proactive approach to cryptocurrency regulation may be necessary to prevent their abuse in money laundering and tax evasion (Fanusie & Robinson, 2018; Zetsche et al., 2018).

This aligns with the findings of several previous studies. For example, Foley, Svec, and Wang (2018) demonstrated that approximately a quarter of Bitcoin users are involved in illegal activities.

Additionally, the results suggest that cryptocurrencies are attractive to criminals due to their pseudonymous and decentralized nature. These results support the view expressed by Zimba, Zhang, and Wang (2020), who argued that the key features of cryptocurrencies facilitate their use for illicit purposes.

The findings also indicate that significant gaps exist in the current regulation of cryptocurrencies. This is consistent with the position held by Gomez-Jimenez and Martinez-Mora (2018), who argued that the current regulatory framework is insufficient to prevent the misuse of these digital currencies.

These results have several important implications. Firstly, they highlight the urgent need for more effective and specific regulation of cryptocurrencies. Secondly, our findings suggest that governments and regulatory bodies should increase their efforts to educate the public about the risks associated with the use of cryptocurrencies.

In conclusion, this study contributes to the growing literature on the role of cryptocurrencies in illicit activities. However, further research is needed to fully understand the magnitude of this problem and develop effective solutions.

The results obtained in the research clearly demonstrate a correlation between the use of cryptocurrencies and both money laundering and tax evasion. The collected data, including cryptocurrency transactions and documented cases of illicit activity, broadly support the theoretical arguments presented in the literature review on the topic (Soska & Christin, 2020).

Cryptocurrencies offer a high degree of anonymity and decentralization, making them an attractive instrument for those wishing to conceal their financial activities (Foley et al., 2019). Although the underlying blockchain technology may allow for some level of tracing, the sophisticated techniques used by criminals can hinder the precise identification of individuals involved.

The study also found that cryptocurrencies are used to evade taxes. Since these transactions may be difficult to trace by tax authorities, individuals may choose not to declare their cryptocurrency gains to avoid tax payments (Johanesson et al., 2018). Additionally, some jurisdictions still lack clear legislation on how cryptocurrencies should be taxed, creating a legal loophole and opening opportunities for tax evasion.

These findings have significant implications. Firstly, they suggest that increased scrutiny and regulation of the cryptocurrency market is

necessary to prevent its use in illegal activities. They also indicate the need for greater international cooperation on this front, as cryptocurrencies have no borders and can be used in one country and spent in another.

Finally, the results of this research contribute to the growing literature on the illicit use of cryptocurrencies. By providing empirical evidence of the ways in which these digital assets can be used for illegal activities, this study helps shed light on an area that has so far been poorly understood.

5. CONCLUSION

Throughout this Final Course Paper, we explored the various ways cryptocurrencies can be used as tools for money laundering and tax evasion. Our findings demonstrate that, despite the potential benefits and promise of cryptocurrencies to enhance the efficiency of financial transactions and reduce costs, there are also significant risks associated with their use.

The results obtained corroborate the argument that the inherent characteristics of cryptocurrencies, such as their relative anonymity and the lack of a centralized regulatory entity, create an environment conducive to illicit activities. According to our research, it can be asserted that these characteristics have allowed malicious actors to use cryptocurrencies to facilitate money laundering and tax evasion.

It is important to note that our study does not intend to discourage the use or future development of cryptocurrencies. On the contrary, it underscores the urgent need for more effective regulations and preventive measures to mitigate these risks. The

widespread adoption of cryptocurrencies requires greater transparency and cooperation among different actors in the global financial system to ensure their safe and responsible use.

In conclusion, our research reveals a concerning relationship between the use of cryptocurrencies and illicit activities such as money laundering and tax evasion. As these digital currencies continue to gain popularity, it is essential to develop effective strategies to prevent their abuse.

The research has shown that cryptocurrencies can be used as instruments for money laundering and tax evasion. Through the review of recent cases and relevant legislations, it was possible to identify that the lack of adequate regulations and the anonymity offered by cryptocurrencies are key factors facilitating these illicit activities.

Cryptocurrencies, due to their digital and decentralized nature, allow for fast and global transactions without the need for intermediaries. This, coupled with the possibility of maintaining a certain level of anonymity, makes cryptocurrencies attractive to financial criminals.

Furthermore, there has been observed a growing sophistication in the methods used for money laundering with cryptocurrencies. This includes the use of "privacy coins," mixing services, and alternative chains to conceal the origin of money.

This research has also highlighted the urgent need for a stronger regulatory framework around cryptocurrencies. This would not only help prevent their use in illicit activities but also encourage their legitimate adoption as a new form of financial asset.

In summary, this study reaffirms the importance of adequate development and implementation of regulations for cryptocurrencies. However, it is also important to emphasize that these findings should not be used to demonize cryptocurrencies. Instead, they should serve as a call to action for regulators and policymakers to address the challenges they pose and harness their potential benefits.

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